

EFFECTIVENESS OF USING AUTHENTIC MATERIALS IN INCREASING LEARNERS

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Annatatsiya: Maskur maqolada autentik materillarni ingliz tilini o'rganishdagi jarayonida qollashning samarali usullari haqida fikr olib borilgan. Shuningdek, mazkur masala olimlar fikrlari keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar : sinfxondagi tadqiqot, ma'no, tushuncha, haqiqiy materiallar.

Annotation: This article provides authentic materials and their importance in increasing learners 'motivation. The article also gives facts which belongs to scientists.

Keywords: classroom investigation, context, concept, real materials.

Аннотация: в этой статье представлены аутентичные материалы и их важность в повышении мотивации учащихся. в этой статье также приведены факт науки по этой.

Ключевые слова: расследование в классе, концепция, контекст, реальные материалы.

We have enough power and possibility, knowledge and ability, definite determination, aspiration and bravery in order to teach special subjects, the history of our country and the civilization of the world, foreign languages and modern computer technologies perfectly to our children and youth.(SH. M. Mirziyoyev)

Over the long periods of time, English has been chosen as an international language to create insouciant atmosphere among diverse nations; it is spoken, mastered and comprehended even in numerous countries. It is clear that English language has already obtained outstanding function in any sphere of life, namely, education, sociology, business, economy, computer programming. Almost in all developing and crucial branches of life success can be result of high English language proficiency since it is the dominant language of technology.

The use of Authentic Materials (AMs) in teaching English has been discussed by many scholars since the approach of Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) appeared in 1970s. Researchers (Peacock, 1997: 144; Porter and Roberts, 1981: 39) found that the more students interact with the real of the target language in the classroom activities, the higher their interest in learning. Aligned with this, Nuttal (2016: 172) points out that authentic text can be motivating because they are proof that the language is used for real-life purposes by real people. Berardo (2006: 64)

notes that one of the reasons why authentic materials are employed in the classroom of English language teaching is to make a close contact with the target language as much as possible. It means that learners are intended to have a direct experience of how the language works in the real situation. The language classroom activities should as far as possible mirror the real world and use the real world or “authentic” sources as the basis for classroom learning.

The topic of article is “Effectiveness of using authentic materials in increasing learners”. The importance of the topic is researching the ways of using authentic materials and teaching the use of them suitably to pupil’s level. The purpose of the theme is to explore the classification of techniques for teaching learning process of a foreign language and developing students’ language skills through authentic materials.

Authentic materials are essential to learn a foreign language, this paper is an attempt to analyze how such materials can be used in the particular situation of learning, especially since our access to materials designed for native speakers of English is virtually unlimited, due to various reasons. We have laid special emphasis on the internet, since we consider it to be an extremely useful and convenient resource..

Most countries have paid much more attention to teaching a foreign language for the last decades. The aim of a foreign language learning is to manage to use it in the real world, in real situation. Furthermore, Language is key to the worl. According to Larsen Freeman (2000, 129), one of the characteristics of communicative language teaching is using authentic materials.

There are several definitions of authentic materials in the field of language teaching. One of the common definitions of the term is given by Kilickaya (2004) „exposure to the real usage of the everyday life language’, (p.1) and how to be used by native speakers on their daily basis. According to Kilickaya, many teachers have discussed that English presented in the classroom should be authentic, not produced for instructional objects. Generally, authentic materials are the materials that involve language naturally occurring as communication in native speaker context of use, or rather those selected contexts where Standard English is the norm: real newspaper report, for example, real magazine articles, real advertisement, cooking recipes, horoscopes, etc. Some general definitions of the term are given by the point of view of the following specialists.

According to Nunan(2016) authentic materials have been created for objects other than to teach language.

Stubbs (2016) describes authentic texts as "actual, attested, and such that they have real authentic examples of use."

Jordan (2017) claims that authentic texts are the ones which are not produced for pedagogical purposes.

Herrington & Oliver (2000) recommended a new pedagogical term, called "authentic learning". This term is related to the students' real life and makes them face and deal with real world situations.

Carter & Nunan (2001, p. 68) defines authentic materials as the materials which are "ordinary texts not produced particularly for teaching language purposes."

Herod (2002) describes authentic learning materials and activities as materials which are produced to imitate the real life situations.

In other words, Jacobson (2003, p:1) defines that authentic materials are used not only in classroom but also in real life situations.

A major part of teaching and learning a foreign language is selecting teaching materials. Nowadays, the resources for teaching materials are available for everybody. Teachers of the foreign language can get many benefits through using different materials, and they can be helpful for the teacher to present the lesson better.

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